

The Analysis of Frequency-Phase Synchronization in Human Cerebral Cortex Activity in Response to Visual Flickering Stimuli

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In this paper, within the framework of the Memory Functions Formalism, we study cooperativity in neural processes, which manifests itself in the effects of frequency-phase synchronization of magnetoencephalogram signals measured at different leads when a person is exposed to flickering light stimuli. During the analysis of the synchronization effects in simultaneously recorded signals, statistical characteristics of the interaction of areas of the cerebral cortex with the most pronounced manifestations of coherence when exposed to flickering stimuli were determined, considering the rhythms of the brain. Stratification of phase portraits of orthogonal dynamic variables, an increase in Markov effects, as well as the intensity of α -, β -activity in the frontal and occipital areas of the cerebral cortex of healthy subjects were discovered when light stimuli were applied. The results obtained will be of interest to specialists whose area of interest is neuroscience, data science or cognitive psychology.

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1. Introduction

In recent years, scientists have been paying special attention to the development of new methods for studying the dynamic states and evolution of complex systems of diverse nature: physical, astrophysical, biological, medical, and social. A complex system is an object consisting of a significant (sometimes enormous) number of interacting components. Such interaction leads to the appearance of new emergent properties of a complex system, such as collective processes and phenomena that cannot be reduced to a

simple sum of correlations between individual parts within a whole. The evolution of complex systems is difficult to model due to competition and interaction between components, as well as their openness, i.e., the exchange of energy and matter with the environment. The study of complex systems is carried out in complexity sciences, data sciences (from data analysis and extraction to big data technologies) and other interdisciplinary scientific fields that are actively developing, primarily due to the exchange and dissemination of scientific ideas [1].

In the totality of complexity sciences, the physics of complex systems stands out. The main tasks of this area are: the application of physical methods in the study of the evolution of complex

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systems, for example statistical physics, as well as the search for physical patterns in describing the behavior and properties of complex systems [2].

The human brain fully exhibits the properties of a complex system. The adult human brain includes over 80 billion neurons, between which neural networks are built - each neuron is connected to 15-20 thousand other neurons (in the case of motor or motor neurons, the number of connections built is significantly greater). All this leads to the fact that trillions of neural connections are manifested in the human brain. The study of the functioning, interaction, self-organization of neurons and neuronal ensembles is of particular interest for neurobiology, neuroengineering, neuroinformatics, artificial intelligence, big data sciences, cognitive psychology [3, 4].

Currently, in medical practice, for research and diagnostics, it is necessary to identify the brain's response to various external (visual, auditory, tactile) or internal stimuli and to link them with brain activity. Frequency-phase synchronization in signals of bioelectrical activity of the human brain is a manifestation of resonant frequencies as a result of the interaction of neuron ensembles - local areas of the cerebral cortex. Activity induced in the cortex by flickering light stimuli is usually recorded as EEG or MEG signals (EEG - electroencephalogram, MEG - magnetoencephalogram) [5, 6]. In addition to flickering, an increase or decrease in activity can be caused by a change in the brightness of the light source, its size or location on the screen [7].

EEG and MEG have an advantage over MRI (MRI - magnetic resonance imaging) in the form of high temporal resolution, while EEG has a lower spatial resolution compared to MEG. The main advantage of MEG is the ability to accurately localize the source of neuromagnetic activity. This is due to the lack of influence of the skull bones and brain tissues on the magnitude of the magnetic field, since they do not interfere with the propagation of magnetic field lines. Consequently, the magnetic field is less distorted on the skull tissues than the electric

field. Therefore, it is possible to record not only the activity of the cerebral cortex, but also subcortical structures. Statistical methods and machine learning algorithms are being developed to analyze the spatiotemporal structures of time series reflecting brain activity [8].

In this paper, within the framework of the Memory Functions Formalism (MFF) - an original theoretical approach to the analysis of temporal signals generated by complex systems, we study the magnetoencephalogram signals of a group of healthy subjects in response to flickering light stimuli of different color combinations (red-blue, red-green, blue-green) [19].

2. Some MFF relationships

MFF is a theoretical approach that allows one to obtain a large set of parameters and dependencies (orthogonal dynamic variables, phase portraits of orthogonal dynamic variables, auto-, cross-correlation functions and related statistical memory functions, measures characterizing the degree of manifestation of statistical memory effects, kinetic and relaxation parameters, etc.) directly from experimentally recorded time signals [10, 11].

In MFF, the cross-correlation function (CCF) is related to the statistical memory functions by the following relationships:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\Delta c(t)}{\Delta t} &= \lambda_1^{XY} c(t) \\ -\tau \Lambda_1^{XY} \sum_{j=0}^{m-1} M_1^{XY}(j\tau) c(t-j\tau), & \\ \dots & \\ \frac{\Delta M_{n-1}^{XY}(t)}{\Delta t} &= \lambda_n^{XY} M_{n-1}^{XY}(t) \\ -\tau \Lambda_n^{XY} \sum_{j=0}^{m-1} M_n^{XY}(j\tau) M_{n-1}^{XY}(t-j\tau). & \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Here λ_1^{XY} is an eigenvalue of the operator \hat{L} , Λ_1^{XY} is a relaxation parameter, $M_1^{XY}(j\tau)$ is a first-order memory function, etc. This chain of

equations is a generalization of the Zwanzig-Mori kinetic theory in statistical physics for cases of cross-correlations in discrete non-Hamiltonian systems and expresses the equations of motion of dynamic variables.

The measure of statistical memory - the non-Markov parameter is introduced to separate stochastic processes into Markov, non-Markov, quasi-Markov, and also to quantitatively assess the effects of memory in the dynamics of the studied time signal. Below is a frequency-dependent case of the non-Markov parameter. Using it, it is possible to establish a change in the patterns in the dynamics of the signals of the processes under study:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_1^{XY}(\nu) &= \sqrt{\frac{\mu_0^{XY}(\nu)}{\mu_1^{XY}(\nu)}}, \\ &\dots \\ \varepsilon_i^{XY}(\nu) &= \sqrt{\frac{\mu_{i-1}^{XY}(\nu)}{\mu_i^{XY}(\nu)}}, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $\mu_i^{XY}(\nu)$ is the power spectrum of the corresponding i -th memory function, which allows us to establish the degree of synchronization depending on the frequency in the mutual dynamics of two signals of the system under study:

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_0^{XY}(\nu) &= \left| \Delta t \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} c(t_j) \cos 2\pi\nu t_j \right|^2, \\ &\dots \\ \mu_i^{XY}(\nu) &= \left| \Delta t \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} M_i^{XY}(t_j) \cos 2\pi\nu t_j \right|^2. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

When $\varepsilon_1^{XY}(0) \gg 1$, the evolution of the system is characterized by a faster decay of the memory function relative to the decay time of the original CCF, and the process is Markov. When $\varepsilon_1^{XY}(0) \leq 1$, then non-Markov effects appear, and the evolution is characterized by long-term (strong) statistical memory. When $\varepsilon_1^{XY}(0) > 1$, a quasi-Markov scenario of the system evolution and moderate statistical memory take place.

In this paper we present only some relationships that allows demonstrating the capabilities of MFF in the analysis of cross-correlations realized in the dynamics of experimentally recorded data of living systems.

3. Experimental data and results of MFF analysis of evoked MEG signals

Experimental biomedical data reflecting the activity of the cerebral cortex are presented as time series of 1841 measurements. Each time series reflects the pulse activity of a certain area of the human cerebral cortex - ensembles of neurons. There are a total of 61 such areas, the activity of which is recorded using superconducting quantum interference sensors (SQUIDs), which are capable of registering magnetic fields with an accuracy of 10^{-15} T. Registration was carried out for a group of 9 healthy subjects (7 men, 2 women) aged 22 to 27 years under the influence of several flickering combinations of light (red-blue, blue-green, red-green) with a frequency of 30 Hz. The first 200 points were recorded before the stimulus was applied. Experimental data were obtained in the course of international collaboration [9, 10].

Previously, the study of MEG signals evoked by the effect of flickering color stimuli on a patient with photosensitive epilepsy (PSE) and a group of healthy subjects [12, 13] allowed identifying "special areas" of the cerebral cortex, the activity of which differed most significantly from the signals of the control group. Additional information on the nature of the dynamic relationship between the identified specific areas of the cerebral cortex was obtained through cross-correlation analysis, which allowed reproducing not only the dynamic picture of pathological rearrangements, but also to develop principles for diagnosing this disease, as well as to propose methods for monitoring the effectiveness of the therapeutic interventions used [10, 14]. Using another theoretical approach, Flicker-Noise Spectroscopy, it was shown that the presence of photosensitive epilepsy leads to a change in

FIG. 1: (color online) Phase portraits composed of one of the combinations of orthogonal dynamic variables, before (d, e, f) and after (a, b, c) the presentation of a red-blue (a, d), red-green (b, e), blue-green (c, f) stimulus.

the ratio between the contributions of burst irregularities and jump irregularities in the dynamics of MEG signals [14, 15]. Violations of the frequency-phase synchronization of the patient's MEG signals were manifested in the dominance of high-frequency components (50-100 Hz) in the power spectra and cross-correlators, reflecting a violation of the interaction of individual areas of the cerebral cortex.

In the present study, we pay special attention to the study of MEG signals recorded from different areas of the cerebral cortex in response to light flickering stimuli in healthy subjects. The purpose of the present study is not only to demonstrate the high individuality of the analyzed signals, but also to search for areas of the cerebral cortex with the most pronounced effects of matching/mismatching, statistical memory taking into account brain rhythms and different color stimuli.

The representative spatiotemporal structure of the signals recorded by these sensors from the frontal and occipital lobes was analyzed based

on phase portraits constructed for a combination of orthogonal dynamic variables. Figure 1(a-f) demonstrates the process of changing the structure of MEG signals when stimuli are applied and when stimuli are changed. When a stimulus is applied, the spatial dimensions of the portraits increase, as well as stratification into two or three unequal structures, indicating a change in the magnitude of the biomagnetic field caused by external influence.

In the course of the analysis of the effects of frequency-phase synchronization in the activity of individual areas of the cerebral cortex of healthy subjects in response to external effects of flickering light stimuli, the power spectrum of the cross-correlation function of first-order memory, as well as the frequency dependence of the information measure of statistical memory - the first point of the non-Markov parameter - were used.

Figure 2 shows the power spectrum of the first-order memory function constructed for the MEG signals of two subjects before and after the

FIG. 2: (color online) Power spectrum of the first-order memory function for neuromagnetic signals of the brain of two healthy subjects (a, c - first volunteer, b, d - second volunteer) before (a, b) and after (c, d) the presentation of a flickering light stimulus for sensors from the frontal and occipital lobes.

flickering light stimulus was applied to the sensors of the frontal and occipital lobes of the human brain. It is evident that the spectrum structure after the stimulus was applied differs significantly from the spectrum structure before the stimulus was applied. The maximum amplitude of the spectra for the first subject changed 10-fold, and for the second subject, 5-fold after the flickering combination was applied. It is important that these bursts characterize the rhythms of brain activity in healthy subjects that form in response to external light exposure. The stimulus causes

a significant reaction - a transition from α -activity to β -activity (in some cases, γ -activity). At the same time, if in the case of the first subject the brain rhythms are clearly detected at frequencies that are multiples of 8-10 Hz, then in the case of the second subject, an overlap of the resonant frequencies by additional periodic processes is observed. This feature may indicate some asynchrony in the activity of neuronal ensembles in the scalp areas of the second subject where the sensors are localized.

Figure 3 shows the averaged maximum

values of the first-order power spectrum for combinations, taking into account the brain rhythms and the influencing light stimuli. The peculiarities include the fact that for each stimulus, β -activity predominates in terms of the average synchronization value. The interaction of these sensors in the θ -rhythm region is the least coordinated, which can be physiologically explained by the fact that a person is in a waking state and the weak activation of the corresponding brain regions in this frequency range when exposed to stimuli. It is also possible to note an increase in synchronization in α -, β -, γ -rhythms when moving from a red-blue stimulus to a red-green or blue-green one.

FIG. 3: (color online) Average values of the maximum values of the 1st order power spectrum for individual combinations of SQUIDs depending on brain rhythms (θ -, α -, β -, γ -activity) and light stimuli on a linear scale.

Figure 4 shows the maximum values of the power spectrum for the specified SQUID combinations, averaged for a group of 9 people and divided by brain rhythms (θ -, α -, β -, γ -rhythms, on the graphs a, b, c, d respectively) on a logarithmic scale when exposed to a blue-green stimulus. Such a representation is convenient for identifying the most synchronized areas of the brain depending on the rhythm (we will limit ourselves to the power spectrum of the

first-order memory function). As can be seen from the graphs, for each rhythm a number of combinations are identified that demonstrate the highest synchronization of signals. In this case, the combinations that demonstrate the highest degree of synchronization are: 10-41, 13-43, 12-47, 11-49, 11-52. In general, the proportion of the most consistent combinations for the blue-green stimulus, associated with α -, β -, γ -rhythms, is greater than for other stimuli.

Quantitative assessment of statistical memory effects using the frequency dependence of the statistical memory measure $\varepsilon_i^{XY}(\nu)$ reflects the change in periodic patterns in the mutual dynamics of certain areas of the cerebral cortex before and after the application of a flickering light stimulus, as well as in cases of transition from one stimulus to another. Figure 5 shows the averaged values of the first point of the non-Markov parameter at zero frequency for a group of 9 people before and after the application of a blue-green stimulus for the specified combinations of sensors. The application of the stimulus leads to the manifestation of Markov features (expressed in an increase in the parameter) in the dynamics of MEG signals recorded by a number of sensors. This fact can be explained by the appearance of many low-amplitude additional periodic processes against the background of resonant frequencies. Before the application of stimuli, dynamics was characterized mainly by non-Markovian effects with rare manifestations of Markovian effects. From a perspective, it can be noted that a comparison of the values of this parameter with the values recorded in patients with disorders of the functions of the cerebral cortex will make it possible to quantitatively determine the change in the type of statistical memory under the influence of stimuli in the mutual dynamics of brain regions.

FIG. 4: (color online) Averaged maximum values of the 1st order power spectrum for individual combinations of SQUIDs with a blue-green stimulus, considering rhythms.

4. Conclusions

In this work within the framework of the Memory Functions Formalism, a statistical analysis of magnetoencephalogram signals of healthy subjects recorded in response to light flickering stimuli of different color combinations is carried out. The Memory Functions Formalism allows analyzing the mutual dynamics of the structural components of complex systems using a set of parameters. Among the parameters studied, we can distinguish combinations of orthogonal dynamic variables, power spectra of memory functions, and information measures of statistical

memory.

In the course of studying the effects of synchronization in simultaneously recorded MEG signals, statistical characteristics of the interaction of areas of the cerebral cortex with the most pronounced manifestations of coordination under the influence of flickering stimuli were determined, considering the rhythms of the brain, a general statistical picture was obtained reflecting the average level of maximum synchronization in rhythms for combinations of SQUIDs from the frontal and occipital areas of the human cerebral cortex. Types of statistical memory characteristic of the interaction of certain

FIG. 5: (color online) Average values of the first point of the non-Markov parameter at zero frequency for individual combinations of SQUIDs before and after the application of a blue-green stimulus.

areas of the brain and features of phase portraits were established.

The results of this work will help to identify the mechanisms of occurrence of abnormal coordination/misalignment in different areas of the human brain in various pathologies. For example, the analysis of EEG and MEG signals will allow establishing statistical (diagnostic) criteria for external influences in patients with neurological and neurodegenerative diseases, such as Parkinson’s disease and photosensitive epilepsy [10, 12–16], as well as with psychiatric disorders (schizophrenia spectrum disorders) [17–

19]. In addition, supplementing the methods of statistical analysis of time signals with machine learning technologies will facilitate the efficient extraction of hidden information from EEG and MEG records, including when human brain activity is exposed to various stimuli [20–25].

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